

DIGITAL DIVERSITY REPORT

Leibniz Institute
DSMZ-German Collection
of Microorganisms
and Cell Cultures GmbH

DSMZ
Digital Diversity

Welcome

We are pleased to introduce our Digital Diversity Report in 2024.

At the Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (DSMZ), we take pride in our position as a prominent provider of biological resources and services for research and industry. Our mission is to advance scientific knowledge by maintaining and distributing high-quality collections of microbial and cell cultures, including our digital collections.

This report offers an overview of our database infrastructure, its importance in scientific research, and the strategic visions for its future evolution.

Warm regards,

the Digital Diversity Team

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Foreword

The Leibniz Institute DSMZ–German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures is the national competence center for the research, provision, and utilization of microbial diversity. It represents one of the largest biological resource centers worldwide. Since the foundation of the DSMZ in 1969, its collections have continuously expanded and meanwhile cover a broad diversity of organisms ranging from *Bacteria*, *Archaea*, fungi, protists, human and animal cell lines, to bacteriophages and plant viruses. The currently 1.2 million DSMZ stocks represent 87,500 different bioresources. In addition, the Leibniz Institute DSMZ provides 6,500 different services to customers per year. As the only International Depositary Authority under the Budapest treaty for microorganisms in Germany, DSMZ is one of the patent repositories with the highest number of deposits in Europe and the world. The unique diversity of resources, its extensive scientific services and the professional quality management makes the DSMZ an international supplier for science, diagnostic laboratories, national reference centers, as well as industrial partners of high renown. Research of the Leibniz Institute DSMZ focuses on microbial diversity and the underlying evolutionary mechanisms (cross-cutting research topic *Systematics & Evolution*), the diversity of microbial functions and adaptations (research topic *Functional Diversity*) and the molecular mechanisms of biotic interactions (research topic *Pathobiology*), resulting in over 100 publications per year.

Previously, data on microbial resources were broadly distributed across numerous heterogeneous sources, little standardized, poor in metadata, and hence could not be directly used for inte-

grative analyses and synthesis work. Fifteen years ago, the Leibniz Institute DSMZ initiated the development of novel, public databases hosting high-quality, well-curated and metadata-rich taxon-associated data. Our long-term goal is to implement a unique, highly enriched, and integrated offer of digital bioresources that complements the existing offer of physical strains and services, allows semantic linkage, is compatible with state-of-the-art applications of machine learning, and thereby creates novel opportunities for knowledge generation and for the future utilization of microbial resources. Until recently, the database work of DSMZ was almost exclusively financed through extramural funds. With the successful acquisition of permanent financial support through a “Kleine Strategische Sondertatbestand” in 2023, DSMZ was able to initiate the establishment of the comprehensive database platform DSMZ Digital Diversity that integrates all current and future database work. The Leibniz Institute DSMZ has the ambition to become a leading digital bioresource center capable of satisfying the changing needs of its scientific user community in the years to come.

Prof. Dr. Jörg Overmann,
Scientific Director, DSMZ

History of Databases at DSMZ

The Leibniz Institute DSMZ is a world-renowned collection of bioresources with a history of more than 50 years. In the first years after its foundation, the DSMZ focused on building up different parts of its collection, including a range of services and patent deposits. In this context, the DSMZ developed in 1993 its first web-based service, Prokaryotic Nomenclature Up-to-Date (PNU), which informed scientists about the nomenclatural changes of prokaryotes.

Since 2010, the DSMZ has laid the foundation for a second pillar of the institute: with the establishment of the Department of Microbial Ecology and Biodiversity Research, a stronger focus on independent research was set. In 2012, this led to the development of the first research-oriented database BacDive, which provides standardised information on prokaryotic strains. The development of BacDive has been a great success, reflected in the increasing number of users worldwide. It has also paved the way for the future development of DSMZ

web services like the Genome-to-Genome Distance Calculator ([GGDC](#)), a web-based tool for sequence-based species delimitation, published first in 2013.

In 2015, the DSMZ became a founding member of the newly established German bioinformatics infrastructure ([de.NBI](#)). Through this, close relations were created with other established web tools and databases, and increased linking and integration of data between resources was driven forward. When de.NBI became the German node of the European bioinformatics network [ELIXIR](#) in 2017, the European stage also opened up for the DSMZ to promote its services and to further develop them according to the [FAIR principles](#).

In 2019, the Type Strain Genome Server (TYGS) platform for high-throughput genome-based taxonomy was developed as a successor to the GGDC. Following that, the LPSN database (List of Prokaryotic names with Standing in Nomenclature), founded by Jean P. Euzéby in 1997, moved to the DSMZ in 2020, merging with the PNU web

Figure 1: Timeline of the databases of DSMZ Digital Diversity. Shown is the first release date of the databases at the DSMZ and (if applicable) also the foundation date for databases that have moved to the DSMZ (in *italics*).

service.

Since 2021, database development at the DSMZ has continued to expand, leading to a broadening of scope to include not only prokaryotes, but also other bioresources: *MediaDive* was first released in 2021, providing culture media and growth condition information for strains from all domains of life; *DSMZCellDive* was developed as a platform for cell line data; and *PhageDive* focuses on bacteriophages.

The development of databases and web services at the DSMZ reached its high point to date in 2022, when a long-forged plan was granted: to establish the new biodata infrastructure DSMZ Digital Diversity with long term financing 22.5 full time equivalents (FTE) at the DSMZ. This not only secured funding to continue the development of the established DSMZ services, but also for the integration of the

two world-renowned databases BRENDA and SILVA to forge a newly integrated infrastructure with impact on the global life science community.

This new chapter started in 2023, when BRENDA and SILVA joined the DSMZ. As the latest resource the new StrainInfo database was relaunched in 2023, providing a web service for microbial strain identity resolution.

Since then, a growing team of biologists, bioinformaticians and software developers has been working intensively to build up the new joint DSMZ Digital Diversity structure at the DSMZ alongside the well-established pillars of collection and research. The focus lies on bioresource data, high quality data through manual curation and high impact web services.

Profiles of DSMZ Databases

BacDive - the Bacterial Diversity Database

The Bacterial Diversity database BacDive is the worldwide largest database for standardised bacterial phenotypic information. Its mission is to mobilise research data on strain level from various sources like the internal files in culture collections or the primary literature. Today BacDive offers 2.6 million data points on 97,334 bacterial and archaeal strains, including 20,060 type strains and thereby covers almost all species with a validly published name. Within over 1,317 data fields the topics taxonomy, morphology, physiology, metabolism, origin, sequence information, and cultivation conditions are covered (Figure 2). The database offers a systematic access to phenotypic data.

Mission and origin

BacDive was founded in 2012 by Jörg Overmann, Carola Söhngen, Adam Podstawka and Boyke Bunk. Within this [GFBio](#) project, data from the DSMZ collection were made searchable for the [GBIF](#) and GFBio search engines. However, this was limited to simple catalogue data. In order to overcome this limitation, a separate SQL database was set up to collect strain-based data providing an extended repertoire of properties. These fields were initially filled with internal DSMZ data and made available on the internet via a graphical interface. The database was intended to provide better access to the diversity of bacteria and was

Figure 2: Overview of the data fields and number of datasets provided by the BacDive database.

therefore called the Bacterial Diversity Database, short *BacDive*.

In the following years, the contents of the database were successively expanded. With the new project to build a German bioinformatics infrastructure ([de.NBI](#)) in 2015, two scientists were hired to further develop the database in terms of content and technology. The number of covered strains could be massively extended by integrating internal data from other culture collections. In order to provide even more comprehensive datasets, a new workflow was established to manually extract up to 130 data fields from species descriptions. The graphical user interface was redesigned and given a responsive design for the use on mobile devices. In addition, search tools were developed to further improve the findability and usability of the data.

Over the years, *BacDive* has become an important database for bacterial data, not least due to its integration and linking data from external databases. A decade of development was crowned by the recognition of *BacDive* as a Global Core Biodata Resource ([GCBR](#)) in 2022 and as an ELIXIR Core Data Resource ([CDR](#)) in 2023. Today, *BacDive* aims to be a central knowledge database for large-scale standardised strain data that promotes findability and usage of information for scientists around the world.

Data collection and curation

Initially, the data were limited to information from the internal databases of the DSMZ. Then, data from private collections like the Reichenbach collection or the Wink compendium on Myxobacteria were integrated. Over time, other large culture

collections (like [CCUG](#), [CIP](#), [JCM](#), and [KCTC](#)) could be convinced to contribute to *BacDive* and provided internal data on their strains. Until today, the strain data from culture collections builds the high-quality backbone of the database.

Besides collection data, the comprehensive data from primary literature, namely the data about type strains in species descriptions, became an important source. In 2016, a first workflow was set up to manually extract and standardise up to 130 data fields from species descriptions. Student researchers were hired to annotate the data. After an initial test phase, including verification of the data, students are able to annotate data with a very low error rate. Additional cross-validation is conducted within the import process by a senior scientist. Up to today comprehensive data from literature on 7,896 strains could be integrated.

To automatically update and extend existing strain data, several routines were established, which are performed during the update process. At first, the database LPSN is used to update current names of strains and amend the synonyms. Moreover, new type strains of species or subspecies with a validly published name are integrated. Routinely, links to sequence information like genomic sequence and 16S sequence are updated and newly found sequence data are integrated from GenBank. In a similar way the literature available is updated and extended. A very important factor of information given in *BacDive* is that data retrieved manually from a curated source and data that are automatically retrieved are clearly differentiated and marked as such. This allows the user to exclude

“non-curated data/information” from the view of a strain page and from retrieval through the web service.

In 2023 the data were extended by genome-based predictions. By providing access to high quality standardised data, BacDive is the source of training data for projects building models for predicting trait data for bacteria ([DeepG](#), [Metatraits](#), [DiASPora project](#)) and we expect many more projects to use the data for the same purpose without our knowledge. Within the DiASPora project, we have started building our own models providing information on oxygen relation, motility, Gram staining, halophily, thermophily, spore building and glucose utilisation. Together with prediction data from other projects, these data are provided in a new section “genome-based predictions”, giving additional information on the method, the genome and the confidence. Predictions exceeding a confidence level of 90% are shown side-by-side with the experimentally determined data. Again, these predicted data are clearly labelled as such. On default these data are not provided through the API, but their inclusion can be actively enabled.

Tools and facilities

As BacDive is a knowledge database, its tools are focused on searching and retrieving data. The most-frequently used tool is the *SimpleSearch* which allows the user to easily find a strain based on its name, culture collection number, NCBI Tax-ID or sequence accession number. Lately, this search function was supplemented with a *SmartSearch*, which recognizes search terms like “glucose” and offers various search options. The *SmartSearch* makes

use of almost 300,000 precalculated *AdvancedSearch* queries and therefore provides a low-level entry into the advanced search options for the users.

The [Advanced Search](#) is the most powerful tool in BacDive and serves the important use case of researchers who want to find strains based on their attributes. Initially the number of search fields was limited and the search fields could not be combined. In 2018, the [Advanced Search](#) was reinvented and now provides 130 search fields that can be used to build complex queries of up to three groups with up to five search fields each. This makes the tool much more powerful, but makes its usage more complicated. It is a constant process to improve the usability to make the entry into using this tool as low as possible, e.g. by improving the overview over the search fields and by providing example queries.

The [Isolation Source Search](#) is a tool to analyse and retrieve data about strains from a specific habitat. Strain datasets typically include only unstructured information on isolation sources. BacDive currently provides information on the isolation sources of 54,578 strains as free text fields comprising anything between single words, like ‘soil’, and long sentences with complex descriptions. To make these data more accessible we established a new 3-level taxonomy of keywords to describe the isolation source and used this to manually ‘classify’ every source. As we found that a binning-system is not sufficient to precisely describe the isolation source, each strain can be described by using up to five sets of keywords. The resulting [Isolation Source Search](#) makes use of this system and enables it to quickly analyse

and retrieve all strains originating from a specific habitat or location.

Besides searching for strains, data retrieval is the most important function. Initially a complex download system was developed for BacDive, following the shopping cart system, allowing users to add strains to a cart and export all the data available for them. Users, though, were often only interested in single data fields, for which reason the export function was adapted to enable selection of data fields to be exported. To further improve access, we added simple export functions to the different search tools, which easily export the queried data as a table. For more advanced users, the [web service \(API\)](#) is available to automatically retrieve large scale datasets. A first RESTful web service was developed in 2015. In 2021 the API was completely renewed, and now features single sign on (including LifeScience Login), [example clients for Python and R](#), and documentation on how to use it.

Usage and recognition

Over the years, BacDive has developed into a comprehensive and stable source for prokaryotic strain and species data, which is used by a community of 25,000 to 38,000 users per month coming from all countries in the world (top five in 2023: US 18%, China 12%, Germany 8%, Japan 5%, UK 4%). To date, BacDive represents the only source that provides comprehensive prokaryotic strain data and serves as a central point of information for researchers to interconnect species names, culture collection numbers, phenotypic information, sequence accession numbers and NCBI tax IDs. Numerous other databases,

including [NCBI](#) databases, [ENA](#), Wikipedia, SILVA, LPSN and BRENDA, are displaying thousands of links that direct users to information on the corresponding strains in BacDive. The greatest achievements of BacDive so far were its recognition as a GCBR (2022) and an ELIXIR CDR (2023).

The use of BacDive covers different appli-

Figure 3: User statistics for the BacDive database since 2015. Shown are unique users per month in blue and returning unique users in green.

cations including biotechnology, medicine, molecular biology, ecology and taxonomy. Users can be coarsely grouped into three use cases: (1) users that look for more information about a specific strain or species, (2) users that want to find a strain featuring certain attributes and (3) users that want to do large scale analysis on standardised data.

The use case of finding more information about a specific strain is supported by the different search options for names, synonyms, and various identifiers in the simple search. Much more important though, is the search machine optimization, by providing rich metadata in a machine-readable format, aligned with [schema.org](#) and [bioschemas.org](#). In 2023, 55% of the visits in BacDive reached the website through a search engine, which emphasised the

importance of search machine optimization.

The use case of finding strains by their attributes is a unique selling point for the *BacDive* database. To our knowledge no other database is providing this function, which is becoming more and more important. This use case is mostly relying on the powerful search options with the [AdvancedSearch](#). However, the search functions are limited by the underlying data and for many strains large gaps of information exist. To fill these gaps several approaches are under development like [acceleration of literature annotation by text mining](#).

Over the years the demand for access to large scale datasets has increased and *BacDive* is again a unique source for comprehensive strain data. The contact with these users is most important, to understand how *BacDive* serves the advance of science. Already years ago, data in *BacDive* was used to predict optimum temperatures based on correlating enzyme annotations with a large set of microbial growth temperatures ([Engqvist 2018](#)). Nowadays, *BacDive* is an often-used training dataset in machine learning approaches, including our own.

Proposed work plan

As of today, the *BacDive* team consists of the group lead Lorenz Reimer, the main web developer Joaquim Sardá, the developer Christian Ebeling and the curator Isabel Schober. Christian Ebeling and Isabel Schober are currently funded by the projects [NFDI4Biodiversity](#) and [NFDI4Microbiota](#), respectively. Additional contributions are made by Julia Koblitz ([Data Integration](#)), Julius Witte ([Bioindustry 4.0](#)) and

Artur Lissin ([StrainInfo/NFDI4Microbiota](#))

One of the major strengths of the *BacDive* database has been its flexibility to integrate new data formats, which led to a relational database providing 1,317 data fields within 87 tables. With the growing complexity of the database, the update process became more and more challenging and time consuming, which strongly affects the flexibility to edit and add content on short notice. To regain flexibility in the development and extension of the database, a transition to a document-based database technology is under development. As a first step, a new frontend representation based on a new JSON-based format is developed that utilises the new DSMZ Digital Diversity design. After that, the database itself will follow, for which the update routines need to be re-implemented. After finishing the transition process, curation and updating the database will be highly flexible and can better react to new developments.

Within the EU project Bioindustry 4.0, the DSMZ is developing together with partners from the Westerdijk Institute and from the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure ([MIRRI](#)) a new common format for exchanging microbial strain data. The aim is to create a new format that is following current schemas ([schema.org/bioschemas.org](#)) which allows to easily retrieve, exchange and update data. To promote this new standard in the future, tools will be developed to transform and use this data format. Moreover, this format will be actively used and provided by the two major strain databases, Strainsbook (MIRRI) and *BacDive*.

A major limitation of the *BacDive* database, how it was originally designed, is

the focus on prokaryotic strains. With the data readily available and the expertise in the DSMZ, initially only data on prokaryotic strains were integrated. Over the years, the database grew and new sources were integrated, disregarding the integration of eukaryotic data. To change this in the future, the aforementioned project BIOINDUSTRY 4.0 will lay the groundwork. The new data format is developed to provide all microbial strain data, including eukaryotes. Moreover, the format enables a new level of data exchange, following the FAIR principles, and will lower the barrier significantly to integrate eukaryotic data from other sources into the *BacDive* database.

Besides the high-quality data from internal files of culture collections the annotation of comprehensive data from primary literature is the most important source for *BacDive*. So far, this approach relies on manual work. A new approach to partly automate the annotation has already been started within the [DiASPora project](#) and is now going to be further developed within the DSMZ Digital Diversity programme together with the databases BRENDA and LPSN as general [annotation suite](#). To better access the knowledge stored in *BacDive*, the development of a dedicated *BacDive* ontology including a graph representation and SPARQL endpoint has been developed in the DiASPora project. As the semantification and linking of data is of major importance for the whole DSMZ Digital Diversity programme, the development is continued and extended as [DSMZ Digital Diversity knowledge graph](#).

One of the most important features of *BacDive* are the metabolic data provided on strain level, that is based on basic data

found in species descriptions and on internal Analytical Profile Index (API) tests. It provides users with a quick overview of the metabolic capabilities of a strain and allows them to search for strains that fulfil certain metabolic criteria, like the production or utilisation of specific metabolites. Within DSMZ Digital Diversity new [organism-centric metabolic pathway maps](#) will be generated for each strain. As *BacDive* integrates only data on the strain level, an often requested feature is an aggregation on the species level or above. Therefore, the development of two new features is planned, providing aggregation of strain-collections like microbiomes and providing species aggregation including the underlying relations of the strains. Furthermore, it is planned to improve the [BacDive Isolation Source Search](#) and its underlying [Microbial Isolation Source Ontology](#) (#MISO) for use in the DSMZ Digital Diversity Hub.

Already in the first concept of *BacDive* in 2012, one of the main focal points was on genomic-phenotypic inference. In recent years, whole genome sequences became widely available for prokaryotic strains and the integration of genomic information to complement the phenotypic data is currently one of the major tasks of *BacDive* development. First in 2023, a new section “genome-based predictions” was established, providing predicted trait data based on machine learning models, using curated *BacDive* data as a training set. In the future, this approach will be further extended through improvement of the underlying genomic data and the development and integration of predicted data for further traits.

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LPSN - the List of Prokaryotic names with Standing in Nomenclature

Due to the rapid changes in prokaryotic nomenclature, and in particular the continuous proposal of new names, expert-curated database systems with semi-automatic data collection are needed to keep track of the literature. [LPSN](#) provides comprehensive information on prokaryotic nomenclature and related data, updated weekly.

Mission and origin

LPSN was founded over two decades ago by a single microbiologist, Jean Paul Euzéby, as a manually curated database. In parallel, the service Prokaryotic Nomenclature Up-to-date (PNU) was established in 1993 as a service of the DSMZ and was curated by Norbert Weiss, Manfred Kracht and Dorothea Gleim. In 2020, after moving to the Leibniz Institute DSMZ and integrating the PNU data, LPSN was relaunched based on a dedicated database infrastructure, including automated data import routines, a database-driven user-friendly website, an application programming interface (API), and a wealth of content-related additions. In December 2023, LPSN was selected by

the Global Biodata Coalition as a Global Core Biodata Resource ([GCBR](#)).

LPSN is the only database supported by the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes ([ICSP](#)), the committee officially responsible for the regulation of prokaryotic nomenclature, the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes ([ICNP](#)), which LPSN implements in a comprehensive and transparent manner. LPSN is unique in the world as an expert-curated, authoritative source of scientific names of prokaryotes and forms the basis of prokaryotic nomenclature for many internationally popular databases. It is also comprehensive, including for each name spelling, etymology, authors, publications, nomenclatural type, synonyms, nomenclatural status and taxonomic status (Figure 4).

LPSN is a knowledge database that integrates data from different sources. LPSN provides fast access for everyone to original literature sources, synonyms, [INSDC](#) accession numbers, sequences of

type-strain 16S rRNA gene sequences, culture collection catalogue entries, entries in *BacDive* and Type (Strain) Genome Server ([TYGS](#)). analyses. In this manner, LPSN promotes reuse of data and software. LPSN puts the shown information into the context of nomenclatural regulations and provides fast access to explanatory data. By implementing the ICNP in an easily accessible way, LPSN assists in setting nomenclatural standards. This includes the nomenclatural status of names of prokaryotes as well as their accurate spelling.

LPSN accelerates and facilitates science by providing free access to names and associated information of microorganisms in strict observance of ICNP, the sole internationally recognized standard for the nomenclature of archaea and bacteria. Names included in LPSN are used in all disciplines that need to refer to prokaryotes. LPSN greatly facilitates scientific communication about microorganisms. The unambiguous nomenclature of microorganisms is of particular importance worldwide, given their role as pathogens of humans, plants or animals, or as biotransformers of food, beverages or the environment.

LPSN is the only source for free access to the names of microorganisms in strict compliance with the ICNP. Anyone using LPSN as an authoritative source for the scientific names of prokaryotes would otherwise be deprived of accurate, comprehensive and up-to-date information on the nomenclature of these microorganisms and would have to undertake extensive literature searches. This applies to individual researchers and similar professionals as well as to other data sources. Taxonomists use LPSN to [describe new taxa](#). Microbiologists

and other users of prokaryotic nomenclature use LPSN to determine which name to apply to which prokaryotic taxon.

Data collection and curation

LPSN provides data on names, nomenclatural types, taxonomic and nomenclatural status, synonymy, etymology, literature, strains, 16S rRNA gene and genome sequences, and a wealth of background information (Figure 5). LPSN searches [PubMed](#), [CrossRef](#) and pertinent journals for suggested or, at least, mentioned names of prokaryotic taxa. [Index Nominum Algorium](#), [NCBI taxonomy](#) and [Catalogue of Life](#) are additional sources of names. All sequence data included in LPSN are retrieved from GenBank (NCBI). LPSN also regularly exchanges data with culture collections.

LPSN imports taxon names from the taxonomic literature. The codes of nomenclature contain all the necessary controlled vocabulary to describe nomenclatural facts. The standard used to evaluate the category, authority, nomenclatural status, nomenclatural type, spelling correctness, and synonyms (if any) of each taxon name is the International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP). The ICNP accepts cyanobacterial names validly published under the International Code of Nomenclature ([ICN](#)), therefore LPSN uses the ICN to evaluate cyanobacterial names. The ICNP does not accept other codes and therefore LPSN does not accept them either, as this would undermine standardisation ([Göker et al. 2022](#)).

The implementation of all of these standards is described online. Virtually all aspects of the ICNP itself are described in detail on LPSN. Background information

Figure 4: Variety of information on prokaryotic names provided by LPSN.

can be found in the [glossary](#), the [FAQ](#) and in the cited literature (e.g. ICNP). For maximum transparency, LPSN provides literature citations for all nomenclatural and taxonomic decisions directly on the pages for each taxon name (e.g. [see Rheinheimeria](#)). Wherever possible, these citations are accompanied by a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and a PubMed ID.

LPSN imports sequences from GenBank using the GenBank flat file format, which includes INDSC identifiers and features. The standards for displaying type strain deposits are those used by the respective [culture collections](#). Similarly, the standards for linking to other resources are the identifiers issued by those resources (including, for example, DOIs and PubMed IDs).

Nomenclatural and taxonomic claims from the literature are automatically accompanied by a date, i.e. the date of publication of that literature source. In order to keep LPSN up to date, new LPSN versions reflecting that literature are created whenever new

taxon names and associated metadata are collected from an additional literature source, usually at intervals of less than a week. For this reason, it is impractical to use versioning for LPSN. Instead, LPSN relies on the publication dates implicit in the cited literature. Further evidence of changes is provided in notes on LPSN taxon pages. Unless automatically generated from LPSN data, annotations on LPSN are also accompanied by a literature citation.

LPSN is maintained and curated by two full-time DSMZ staff. LPSN also employs student assistants for simpler data curation tasks, whose contribution is approximately equivalent to a half-time employee. Additional student assistants will be hired based on funding received from the ICSP. LPSN uses the IT and computing infrastructure of the DSMZ. The necessary hardware is managed by the DSMZ system administrators.

Tools and facilities

LPSN uses a record number for each taxon name, which can be used to create a stable link to LPSN's web page for that taxon name (e.g. 779441 gives <https://lpsn.dsmz.de/taxon/779441>). Name-based URLs are also stable (e.g. [Phaeobacter inhibens](#)).

As of September 2023, LPSN has linked as follows. For about 23,000 different strains, INSDC identifiers link to ENA and NCBI. Deposit numbers link to catalogues of 57 different culture collections in c. 62,200 cases. BacDive identifiers are used to link to BacDive strain records. Approximately 22,900 different DOIs and c. 20,500 PubMed IDs link to literature sources.

Sequence data are provided in FASTA format, phylogenetic trees (via the DSMZ single-gene phylogeny server) in Newick format. In addition to the website, data can be accessed and downloaded via the [LPSN API](#) and via [CSV download](#). The LPSN API provides data in JSON [format](#). LPSN record numbers are included in the CSV download and in the API records.

LPSN provides a detailed overview of the [terms](#) used in prokaryotic nomenclature. Links to glossary entries for each term of relevance are found on each taxon name page. A large number of notes on these pages provide additional guidance. [Navigation](#) through LPSN is easy. The [advanced search](#) form provides examples directly. LPSN provides an up-to-date list of publications on [nomenclature](#). LPSN also publishes on these topics (e.g. [Arahal et al. 2023](#); [BISMIS Live](#)).

LPSN operates a help desk, which can be accessed via a [web form](#). All requests create tickets which are submitted to and

answered by the database team. All replies and further requests are recorded in the ticket system for traceability. LPSN additionally provides answers to Frequently Asked Questions ([FAQ](#)). As of 2024, LPSN is also present on social media ([Twitter: LPSN_DSMZ](#); [Mastodon: @lpsn](#); [Bluesky: lpsn.bsky.social](#)).

The latest LPSN news and a list of the most recent taxon names can be found on the LPSN [home page](#). Up-to-date [figures](#) on LPSN-related [statistics](#) are also available and free for use. LPSN publishes descriptions of important developments in the resource at regular intervals ([Meier-Kolthoff et al. 2022](#)). Users of LPSN can also subscribe to LPSN's [mailing list](#) to be kept informed.

Some users provide feedback directly through our help desk. In addition, LPSN collects feedback on user experience through surveys. These are announced on the website and via the mailing list. LPSN itself also participates in proposals for the underlying rules of prokaryotic nomenclature (e.g. [Göker & Oren 2023](#)), thus also incorporating user feedback. Users can also anonymously [suggest taxon names](#) for inclusion in LPSN. These will be included once LPSN has confirmed that the publication in question has indeed proposed the name.

Each month LPSN informs culture collections of newly recorded or questionable deposits, new publications and spelling corrections. Authors of not validly published taxon names are encouraged to submit validation requests on a monthly basis. Once per year the ICSP subcommittees on taxonomy receive a list of taxon names within their scope.

Usage and recognition

Papers on LPSN are recognised as highly cited, although many publications simply cite the URL of the website. The two most recent LPSN publications ([Parte et al. 2020](#) and [Meier-Kolthoff et al. 2022](#)) are flagged as highly cited resources in Web of Science (the 2020 LPSN publication and the 2022 TYGS/LPSN update publication have already been cited more than 683 and 340 times respectively). A Web of Science analysis of the most recent LPSN publication in April 2023 revealed the following top ten research fields citing LPSN: Microbiology, Biotechnology Applied Microbiology, Biochemistry Molecular Biology, Food Science Technology, Infectious Diseases, Environmental Sciences, Genetics Heredity, Pharmacology Pharmacy, Multidisciplinary Sciences, and Marine Freshwater Biology.

Since its relaunch in February 2020, LPSN has been accessed from the vast majority of countries of the world. Over the years, the number of unique visits increased but especially the distinct increase of returning visits indicate that users repeatedly access LPSN (Figure 5). In 2023, LPSN was visited by between 28,600 and 43,000 unique users per month (average 34,000), generating between 53,500 and 81,900 visits and between 266,700 and 823,700 page views per month. These visitors were located on six continents, Asia 46.5%, Europe 28.1%, North America 17.2%, South America 4.3%, Africa 1.9% and Oceania 1.3% with the top five countries being China (24.2%), United States (13.5%), Japan (7.5%), Germany (5.5%) and South Korea (4%).

LPSN's pages of interest are indeed easy to find. In 2022, 46.0% of all visitors came to LPSN via search engines (mainly Google),

while 45.6% came directly. Visitors from other sites came mainly from BacDive (15,730 visits), Wikipedia, DSMZ, NCBI and CDC (1,443 visits). LPSN's quick search is also easy to use; according to Matomo it has been used 321,783 times (2020), 468,351 times (2021) and 488,484 times (2022) in recent years. If required, the advanced search is available and has been used 15,792 (2020), 15,263 (2021) and 23,898 (2022) times in recent years. LPSN's API has been accessed from 66 distinct countries; overall 1,696 users have registered for it originating from 74 countries.

LPSN is used in many countries by hospitals, universities, culture collections, research institutions, microbiological service providers and industry to determine how to name prokaryotes. The International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology uses the LPSN API to check manuscripts during typesetting.

Figure 5: User statistics for the LPSN database since 2020. Shown are unique users per month in blue and returning unique users in green.

LPSN is linked to or from databases such as BacDive, SILVA, TYGS, Catalogue of Life and GTDB, and from culture collection catalogues such as DSMZ, CCUG and CECT. A total of 92,237 strain pages in BacDive link

to LPSN pages for each covered taxonomic rank, resulting in a total of 645,659 links. Wikipedia contains 18,936 links to LPSN. LPSN is used by the NCBI taxonomy, although links to LPSN are not necessarily provided. Commercial users that provide identification tools and other services for medical and industrial microbiology, such as [SmartGene](#), link to LPSN, as do government agencies such as the German Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health and scientific journals.

Proposed work plan

Accompanying the ongoing import and curation of nomenclature-related information, LPSN has started in 2023 to extend the grammatical and orthographic correction of names, reinforcing LPSN's role as a spelling standard. LPSN is also used on an ongoing basis to detect names and taxonomic claims that violate the ICNP. Formal nomenclature proposals on these issues will be published in the next years.

As a literature-driven database, LPSN relies on cited references for its higher-level classifications. In 2023, additional literature sources have been collected, including the primary source for taxonomic relationships wherever possible. The final changes needed to implement LPSN's "concept consistency" for all taxa above genus rank have been made already in 2023. This will be followed by the extension of the scope of the API to include validly published names above genus rank, including the newly accepted kingdom rank, which will also be added to LPSN's hierarchical classification.

Extensions to the API to provide more information per name have mainly been driven by user suggestions and the needs

of databases such as SILVA. Further extensions will be implemented based on external demand and ICNP emendations. In parallel, the LPSN advanced search will be extended.

A recent emendation of the ICNP has been the recognition of cyanobacterial names validly published under the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi and plants (ICN). Since its relaunch, LPSN has collected thousands of cyanobacterial names and intends to complete this collection in 2025, accompanied by further additions to the database's checks for full implementation of the ICN.

Additionally, LPSN's routines for finding the literature of interest and for finding the proposals of names within that literature have been continuously expanded and improved. More sources will be integrated by 2025, including Europe PMC and Scopus.

To improve the LPSN web interface, it will include more external links, such as those to other DSMZ Digital Diversity databases, and more internal links to other LPSN pages. Additionally, a user survey on the LPSN interface will be conducted to further improve the individual pages. Modernisation and standardisation of the layout will be carried out as required.

In addition to record numbers, LPSN envisages the introduction of DOIs for even more robust linking to taxon names. A stand-alone LPSN tool or API could then be made available for checking or annotating documents with such links, including checking the spelling and status of taxon names. A tool for checking taxonomic classifications for compliance with the ICNP may also be provided. The LPSN classification itself will be extended to include phylogeny-based

checks, in line with the expansion of the [TYGS](#).

LPSN has already integrated the classification of bacteria into risk groups from several countries. In collaboration with a recently established subgroup of the ICSP, LPSN will aim to further integrate such data to provide taxonomic choices that better reflect the needs of practitioners. Lists of nomenclatural acts (new names, “name changes”) for defined groups of taxa and defined time periods may also be provided, including recommendations for name choices.

Meier-Kolthoff, J. P., Carbasse, J. S., Peinado-Olarte, R. L., & Göker, M. (2022). TYGS and LPSN: a database tandem for fast and reliable genome-based classification and nomenclature of prokaryotes. *Nucleic acids research*, 50(D1), D801–D807. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab902>

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BRENDA - the Enzyme Information System

Mission and origin

BRENDA (www.brenda-enzymes.org) is the world’s main information site for functional enzyme and ligand-related information and metabolism data. It was founded in 1987 at the German National Research Centre for Biotechnology in Braunschweig (GBF, now [HZI](#): Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research). From 1996–2007 it was continued at the University of Cologne and returned to Braunschweig to the Department of Bioinformatics and Systems Biology at the Technische Universität Braunschweig. It is now located at the Systems Biology Centre Braunschweig ([BRICS](#)). Since the beginning of 2023, BRENDA is part of the Leibniz Institute DSMZ Digital Diversity and as of the beginning of 2024, all BRENDA services are now running on a new DSMZ-hosted IT infrastructure.

As an [ELIXIR Core Data resource](#) (since 2018) and partner of the German network

of bioinformatics de.NBI (since 2015), BRENDA is in close collaboration with other biodata resources. In 2022 BRENDA was appointed by the Global Biodata Coalition to [Global Core Biodata Resource](#). Funding has been obtained from the EU and national sources.

BRENDA was originally published as a series of books (Handbook of Enzymes). But from the beginning on the vision was to collect the fast-growing number of published enzyme data and information in literature references and provide them in a database as a retrieval system. In 1998, the collection of information was transformed into a publicly available database with a simple query system.

The continuous integration of new high-quality data and new developments in BRENDA is essential to meet the requirements of the users in the scientific community in the fields of systems biology,

biotechnology, medical and pharmaceutical research. For this purpose, the database offers a broad variety of data fields on enzyme properties, enzyme-ligand-interactions, functions, occurrences, diseases, and applications.

The BRENDA database provides highly advanced query systems as well as evaluation and visualisation tools for a quick and detailed assessment of enzyme properties. Basis of this biodata resource is a huge collection of data, manually extracted and evaluated from primary literature. This is combined with additional information obtained by text and data mining, data integration, and prediction algorithms. BRENDA is not limited to a specific aspect of the enzyme or to a specific organism. The manually curated core contains about 5.4 million experimentally derived functional and property data of ~104,000 enzymes from ~14,000 different organisms, and ~260,000 ligands extracted from ~167,000 references. Each data entry is connected to the literature reference and the source organism. In addition, pathways, taxonomy information, sequences and 3D structures from other databases, predicted enzyme locations and genome annotations, and ~1.7 million functional and 2D structural data are stored in BRENDA.

Data collection and curation

The database is developed by curation of all well-characterised enzymes of the global literature. The enzymes are assigned to EC numbers based on the [classification system of the IUBMB](#) (International Union of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology) according to the catalysed reactions, in close

[cooperation](#) with the BRENDA team.

BRENDA data are extracted from the primary literature either manually or by text mining (and identified as such: AMENDA and FRENDA). In addition to the manually extracted information, BRENDA integrates data of further external databases like [IUBMB ExplorEnz](#), [PubMed](#), [UniProt](#), [PDB](#), [BacDive](#), [NCBI-MeSH](#) and provides links to other databases (i.e. [PROSITE](#), [InterPro](#)). Since [NCBI Taxonomy](#) identifiers are now available in [BacDive](#) the number of links from organism related pages in BRENDA to [BacDive](#) has increased by orders of magnitude. Each single entry is connected to a reference, covering the literature between 1939 and 2024. It is also connected to an organism, and where available to a strain and a sequence identifier for the enzyme-protein. The manually annotated data cover [50 categories](#) grouped into 'Nomenclature', 'Enzyme-Ligand Interactions', 'Diseases', 'Functional Parameters', 'Organism-related Information', 'General Information', 'Enzyme Structure', 'Molecular Properties', 'Applications', 'References'. Each EC class is updated periodically and data from selected new references are annotated, and included. Newly classified enzymes approved by the IUBMB are integrated promptly.

The manual selection of relevant papers from PubMed and [Scopus](#) is a crucial step. 2.6 million papers are listed in PubMed under the MeSH (Medical Subject Headings) term "enzymes", more than 120,000 of which appeared in 2023 and 2024. This means that only a tiny fraction of all papers can be exploited and the goal of the selection process is to identify those papers providing a large amount of data

about the enzyme in question. Depending on the state of knowledge for a certain enzyme, between 1 and 632 papers build up the knowledge base. The literature search is based on a combined search in PubMed and Scopus using terms related to the data categories (Figure 6) in BRENDA, i.e. enzyme names (i.e. 113,688 distinct enzyme names and 8,423 EC numbers), enzyme function, reactions (substrates/products), and occurrence (organism, tissues etc.). After the manual selection and analysis steps the relevant literature is annotated by highly qualified scientists. The current BRENDA release (2023.1) covers active 7,216 current enzyme classes (EC numbers). BRENDA also contains “preliminary BRENDA-supplied EC numbers”.

Information on compounds interacting with enzymes such as substrates and products, cofactors, inhibiting and activating substances constitute a major part of BRENDA. Currently BRENDA stores ~259,500 ligand names with ~ 161,000 different molecular structures. There are chemical compounds for which BRENDA stores up to 76 different names annotated from the literature. 27,700 compounds possess at least two names. An exact mapping of synonymous ligand names is only possible via a comparison of their chemical structures. This means that for all ligands the chemical structure has to be included, in most cases hand drawn and stored as “Molfiles”, InChI codes and figures.

The data that are manually extracted from each paper are channelled through an elaborate control workflow starting with hundreds of different computer-based checks controlling the formal accuracy and the internal consistency of the data. This is

followed by manual controls by two internal scientists. This process guarantees high quality of the data before they are further processed for the final BRENDA database release.

Tools and facilities

The manually annotated high-quality data that form the core of BRENDA, are supplemented by information retrieved by text mining from PubMed literature titles and abstracts, containing ~1.6 million entries from ~3.4 million references including information on enzyme-disease relationships, tissues, cellular and subcellular localization, and kinetic data stored in the accessory repositories [DRENDA](#), [FRENDA](#), [AMENDA](#), and [KENDA](#).

BRENDA offers diverse search options for retrieving the extensive information. In general, there are text- and graphic based-searches. A simple search provides a quick access and overview of enzyme information, for example via the [Enzyme Summary Page](#).

Another essential part is constituted by the BRENDA ligands. Detailed ligand information is available using the [structure-based queries](#) or the [Ligand Summary Page](#), which contains the corresponding enzyme data, pathways and structural information

In addition to the queries for enzyme and ligand information, the visualisation of data is another key feature of BRENDA. Since 2016 BRENDA has integrated [pathway maps](#) showing enzymes in their metabolic context. The current map contains 188 pathways of different sizes with 11,465 nodes for metabolites and enzymes and 12,096 edges which combine enzymes and

reactants to reactions. Almost all reactions are connected to EC classes.

BRENDA offers two types of word maps giving a quick overview on enzyme research areas visualising enzyme-specific terms in [enzyme word maps](#) and organism-related terms in [organism word maps](#), occurring in PubMed titles and abstracts.

Beyond the regular database query BRENDA offers a large number of tools that allow the user to answer a wide range of questions with BRENDA, some of which will be briefly highlighted in the following. The [Localization Prediction tool](#) gives possible subcellular localisations for enzymes like secretory pathway, chloroplast, and mitochondrion. The [EnzymeDetector](#) provides an integrative overview of enzymatic function annotations obtained from major annotation hosts supplemented with prediction results for 10,200 organisms

(Archaea, Bacteria, and Eukarya) and 24 million genes.

Furthermore, BRENDA allows access to diverse enzyme-related ontologies, such as the in-house developed [BRENDA Tissue Ontology](#) (BTO). It provides a structured comprehensive encyclopaedia of tissue terms from multicellular organisms. These terms provide access to data of enzymes isolated from or detected in the respective tissues, cell types, or cell lines. Thus the BTO also serves as a starting point for tissue specific enzyme data queries. Additionally, the human anatomy atlas [CAVE-man](#) is linked to the BTO terms providing a connection between anatomical and functional enzyme data.

As BRENDA provides organism-specific data, the website allows access to enzyme information starting from a taxon via the [TaxTree Explorer](#), which is based on the

Figure 6: Categories of data fields in BRENDA.

NCBI Taxonomy. In another approach, the ‘[Genome Explorer](#)’ can be used for browsing and comparing enzyme annotations in complete genomes. This allows the user to visualise the genomic environment of the gene of interest in different organisms. For the comparison of enzyme-catalysed reactions, the user can employ the [BKMS-react](#) module in BRENDA to enter, e.g., enzyme names, substrates or products. As a result, all matching enzyme-catalysed reactions of the four substance databases BRENDA, [KEGG](#), [MetaCyc](#), and [SABIO-RK](#) are displayed in comparison.

Usage and recognition

BRENDA has been accessible via the World Wide Web since 1998 and has developed into an indispensable encyclopaedia that meets the needs of users in connection with the rapidly growing amount of data (“Big Data”) and new developments in the “OMICS” community in the fields of systems biology, biochemistry, biotechnology, medical and pharmaceutical research. This is also reflected in the appointment of BRENDA as GCBR and ELIXIR CDR. The data are otherwise only accessible by reading many thousands of publications, whereas in BRENDA the global literature of all well-characterised enzymes is manually curated and structured, which is the only way to compare different product development approaches.

BRENDA is visited by between 23,000 and 47,000 users per month, generating between 165,000 and 371,000 page views per month. Due to the sustainable continuity of BRENDA, the migration process and future planning, no developments were made to

the current BRENDA website in 2022 and 2023. For this reason, we expected and accepted a slight decrease in user numbers. Despite this, our user numbers remain at a high level. Monthly data can only be tracked back until January 2017 due to a limitation of data retention in Google Analytics. The switch to the new web analytics platform Matomo took place in April 2022 (Figure 7). BRENDA is visited virtually from all countries worldwide. The large number of users originate from Asia 36.6%, Europe 29.8%, North America 24.8%, South America 5.5%, Africa 1.8% and Oceania/Australia 1% (according to IP addresses tracked from February 2023 – February 2024), focusing on the top five countries China 17.2%, USA 14.5%, Mexico 7.2%, Germany 5.9%, and Japan 4.9%. The developers participate in international standardisation groups and efforts like the IUBMB/IUPAC enzyme commission and nomenclature committee and the BioPortal for the development of a tissue and enzyme source ontology.

Figure 7: User statistics for the BRENDA database since 2017. Shown are unique users per month in blue and returning unique users in green.

In the 37 years of existence, in addition to the integration of high-quality curated data and the development of new tools it

has always been important for BRENDA to establish the knowledge exchange and interaction with users. The importance of scientific publications is reflected by more than 5,700 citations of BRENDA articles within the last 20 years (Google Scholar Analysis).

BRENDA offers training courses, [tutorials](#), [videos](#), workshops, and user events to learn more about user experiences and wishes through direct exchange. In addition, the user can ask questions or give feedback directly via the ticket system of the BRENDA support ([DSMZ Digital Diversity Helpdesk](#)). Further opportunities to exchange news and information published on social media ([Facebook](#), [X](#), [Instagram](#)).

This offer will be extended with regard to the [DSMZ Digital Diversity](#) to present the linking and analysis of different types of life science data from all resources and to demonstrate access to this unique research data infrastructure.

Proposed work plan

Since January 2023 BRENDA has been located at the DSMZ and permanently funded as part of the DSMZ Digital Diversity. In 2023 the migration of the server systems was the main focus of all team members, nevertheless, a BRENDA Update (version 2023.1) with new data could be released.

The main task of updating the BRENDA core data with manual annotation is an ongoing process, including general update and optimisation procedures. Tasks such as the further development of BRENDA Pathway Maps, the optimization and expansion of text mining methods, as well as the integration of prediction tools, such as

the prediction of protein 3D structures, are being pursued within the framework of the DSMZ Digital Diversity to gain new scientific knowledge.

This also includes the development of tools for analysing metabolic and enzymatic data, together with the *BacDive* database. In cooperation with the [DSMZCellDive database](#), a linking of EC numbers and genes will be realised. A visualisation will be implemented on the enzyme summary page, which displays the top 10 enzyme-expressing cell lines in a bar chart.

In this context the focus is on the extensive further development of the BRENDA Pathway Maps, which will also take time beyond 2025. Based on the existing maps and the comprehensive organism-specific enzyme-ligand data, the BRENDA team will create organism-specific maps, in close cooperation with the group “Data Integration”.

Based on this, the integration of new metabolic pathways will be continuously manually processed, with the expertise in enzyme classification and biochemical reactions, as part of the [Enzyme Nomenclature Committee](#) of the IUBMB. Another focus will be the integration of signal transduction pathways, supported by the DSMZ group “Human and Animal Cell Lines” and DSMZCellDive, with the intention of mapping uploaded expression data on the pathway maps in the future. This project will require a lot of manual work and time and will thus extend beyond 2025.

Furthermore, the renewal and improvement of the BRENDA website (back- and front-end) will be another important project in order to adapt to the user’s needs and wishes. User analysis and user feedback

are important factors to learn about their workflow, and how BRENDA within the Digital Diversity Hub and as a standalone database could support their research activities. The accessibility and visualisation of data and information are increasingly important in today's life science world. This also includes the linking of the BRENDA data to the data resources within the Digital Diversity Hub and internal databases of the DSMZ to open up further user groups.

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SILVA - high quality ribosomal RNA databases

[SILVA](#) (lat. forest) is the most comprehensive resource for quality-controlled datasets of aligned ribosomal RNA (rRNA) gene sequences from all domains of life. It is the only rRNA database worldwide which includes eukaryotes, provides datasets for the rRNAs of the small (SSU) and large (LSU) subunits of the ribosome, and gives special emphasis to the consistent naming of clades solely comprising uncultivated microorganisms.

Mission and origin

The [ARB](#) (lat. arbor = tree) workbench was created in 1991 at the Technical University of Munich to support high-quality phylogenetic inference and taxonomy based on rRNA marker genes. Initially, the ARB project also maintained reference datasets. After a massive increase in publicly available sequence data, manual maintenance of the datasets was no longer possible. At the same time, the need for high-quality reference datasets grew all over the world. To fill this gap, the SILVA project was started at the Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology in Bremen. This decoupled

the maintenance of the reference datasets from the maintenance of the ARB software. Beginning with its first public release in 2007, SILVA's mission was to serve as an essential resource for studying microbial diversity, evolution, and ecology by providing comprehensive and accurate reference datasets of rRNA gene sequences and associated information.

In the following years, the SILVA team focused on publishing new releases and extending its online services. For example, the TestProbe and TestPrime tools to enable web-based in-silico evaluation of probes and primers were added. The next key date in the history of SILVA came in 2014 when [SILVAngs](#), an analysis service for next generation amplicon data was launched. In 2015, SILVA became a founding member of [de.NBI](#). In 2016, Germany joined [ELIXIR](#) and made de.NBI the German ELIXIR node. Therefore, SILVA also became a founding member of ELIXIR Germany.

After Germany joined ELIXIR, SILVA successfully applied as [ELIXIR Core Data Resource](#) and was named such in 2018. In the following years, the SILVA team worked

hard on securing the future of SILVA via permanent funding. This process took longer than expected due to the COVID 19 crisis. During the elongated process SILVA lost its last founding member of the development team at the end of 2021 to a call from industry. The quest for permanent funding was finally completed when SILVA

joined the DSMZ at the beginning of 2023. In December 2023, SILVA's importance on global scale was underlined by its designation as [Global Core Biodata Resource](#).

Today's applications of SILVA range from environmental science, microbiology, agriculture, biochemistry, biotechnology, biodiversity analysis, and medicine to quality control in science and industry.

Data collection and curation

All sequences in SILVA are obtained from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). SILVA releases are created using a semi-manual workflow, which together with metadata sources is shown in Figure 8. To align all potential ribosomal RNA sequences, SILVA uses a manually curated reference alignment (SEED), which is undisclosed due to confidentiality agreements with sequence providers. Additional sequences are added to the SEED when a more detailed alignment is required for a specific phylogenetic branch. These sequences are typically novel and require significant effort to ensure their validity. Publication rights cannot be requested for these findings.

SILVA maintains a taxonomic resource for the SSU and LSU rRNA sequences of Prokaryota and Eukaryota, respectively. The SILVA taxonomy integrates

Figure 8: The SILVA release is created by retrieving sequence data and associated metadata from the European Nucleotide Archive and scanning for potential ribosomal RNA sequences. Additional metadata are added from public sources. The initial processing involves removing low-quality sequences and preparing the datasets for manual taxonomic curation. Following the curation of the de-replicated high-quality subsets, the taxonomic classification is automatically transferred to the replicates and lower quality sequences. Finally, the data are exported and provided to our users in various formats through our services.

information from several external resources of nomenclature and classification, including [Bergey's Manual Trust](#), [GTDB](#), [LPSN](#), [UniEuk](#), and [NCBI](#). We accept a limited amount of personal communications (referred to as Users) before publication, when provided data are scientifically sound, of high impact, and come from authorities in the relevant taxonomic area. The SILVA taxonomy is created through a semi-automatic process of data curation to classify each sequence entry up to the genus level. The manual curation process starts by choosing a point in time to stop considering new changes in external resources. Small errors in lineages, such as typos and misassignments, are corrected to maintain the SILVA taxonomy. Significant taxonomy changes that were published in the *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* ([IJSEM](#)) are also adopted. Sometimes, it is necessary to synchronise the SILVA taxonomy with an external resource or fill in missing information down to the genus level. These taxonomy changes are applied to the reduced redundancy versions of SILVA's high-quality subsets (SSU/LSU Ref NR 99). Our taxonomic assessment follows the phylogenetic trees of these subsets.

During the [BISMis Meeting 2016](#) and the [ISME 2018](#), Bergey's Manual Trust, GTDB, and SILVA discussed integrating relevant updates from the GTDB taxonomy. Before adopting any changes, we ensure their consistency with our 16S rRNA phylogenetic schema. In general, both phylogenies are consistent, resulting in a similar taxonomy in both resources. In cases of strong disagreement, we reject a GTDB taxonomy proposal and keep the former 16S rRNA schema. We are aware of the significant

taxonomy changes that GTDB has created and continues to create. Therefore, we have welcomed all positive and negative opinions from our user community regarding this matter.

Tools and facilities

SILVA supports users in analysing rRNA sequencing data on different levels. For non-bioinformaticians, the website offers several user-friendly tools. Sequences from specific microorganisms of the user's choice can be downloaded using the search tool. The user can use the extended and detailed [search](#) function or browse through the taxonomic order to find sequences of interest by using the SILVA [browser](#).

If a user wants to sequence the rRNA gene for a more specific group of microorganisms, the [TestProbe](#) tool can be used to check if the selected primer sequence has a good number of hits in the SILVA database and [TestPrime](#) can be used to evaluate the primer pair. Once the specific region has been sequenced, the user can go back to SILVA and use the [ACT](#) tool (alignment, classification and tree service) to align the sequences with each other, classify them and calculate a phylogenetic tree, all in one setting. The ACT consists of three services: The SINA aligner aligns the user's sequences to the global SILVA seed alignment of rRNA genes. Subsequently, SINA then classifies the sequences using the Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA) method and the taxonomies provided by SILVA. The phylogenetic tree is then calculated using [RaxML](#) or [FastTree](#). The user can choose between several settings, all of which can be done in a user-friendly interface on the website.

Scientists working with rRNA sequences from high-throughput sequencing (NGS) often use SILVA to identify the microbial community of their samples. The [SILVAngs](#) tool can be used to analyse and classify amplicon sequencing data. This is particularly helpful for scientists who lack computational resources and are less experienced in bioinformatics. However, the curated SILVA datasets are also often used by experienced bioinformaticians as reference dataset for their pipelines (e.g. [QIIME2](#), [DADA2](#), [mothur](#)).

SILVA provides detailed online tutorials for its [search](#) as well as for the [TestProbe](#), [TestPrime](#) and [ACT](#) tools directly on the SILVA website. For SILVAngs, a [user manual](#) and a [demo project](#) are available.

Usage and recognition

Since its creation, SILVA has been used by researchers from almost every country in the world. In 2023, 36.3% of users were from Asia, 32.5% from Europe, 27.9% from the Americas, 1.6% from Africa, and 1.5% from Oceania. The United States (19.2%), China (18.9%), Germany (6.5%), Japan (4.5%) and France (3.4%) were the top five countries of origin. In total, SILVA had more than 85,000 users (6,974 to 10,992 per month) who made more than 165,000 visits (10,891 to 16,606 per month). For these users, almost 63,200 jobs were executed on the SILVA website and 129,000 downloads from our archive were recorded. At the end of last year, SILVAngs had more than 9,000 registered users, for whom 1,891 projects with more than 120.9 billion bases were successfully processed in 2023. The Google Scholar data shows that SILVA is very important for the scientific community. In

2023, SILVA's publications were cited more than 5,500 times (more than 34,000 times in total, as of 17 April 2024). [Dimensions reports for the SILVA update paper](#) (Quast et al. 2013) that compared to other publications in the same field, this publication is extremely highly cited and has received approximately 1659 times more citations than average.

Figure 9: User statistics for the SILVA database since 2007. Shown are unique users per month in blue and returning unique users in green.

The web statistics for 2023 are a mixture of data from Matomo and Google Analytics (until 15 / 28 February for SILVAngs / SILVA), as a switch in the employed service was necessary with the migration of SILVA to the DSMZ. This led to inconsistencies in the unique user counts, as Matomo doesn't know which user Google has already seen and when. In addition, we noticed a significant drop in users compared to 2022 (-21.2%) after switching to Matomo. We can't explain the difference yet, but we believe that the drop does not represent a significant loss of real users. The BRENDA team observed a smaller but still significant drop when making the same change, and our publications were cited only 1.2% less than in 2022. Unfortunately, hardware failures at the DSMZ caused the SILVA website jobs to be unavailable for more than six

weeks.

SILVA is part of the [UniEuk](#) project (Universal taxonomic framework and integrated reference gene databases for Eukaryotic biology, ecology, and evolution) in which we are responsible for the development of a taxonomic curation platform ([EukMap](#)), which we plan to use for the SILVA taxonomy to make its evolution more transparent to the user (DSMZ: in-kind contribution). Through the EukMap application, SILVA was part of the ELIXIR implementation study [APICURON](#) (2022/23), during which the application was extended to include optional public tracking of curation efforts (DSMZ: in-kind contribution). The [FAR-DSI](#) project (Feasibility Assessment of Regulation for Digital Sequence Information) selected SILVA as a member of their sounding board to provide the perspective of a sequence database.

Users can contact the SILVA team via mail (contact@arb-silva.de, ngs-contact@arb-silva.de) or use the [DSMZ Digital Diversity Helpdesk](#) for any questions or feedback. SILVA also uses the social media platform [X](#) to exchange further information with the community.

Proposed work plan

Releases

Releases 138.2 and 144.1 will be update releases, updating the SILVA taxonomy only, whereas full releases 144 and 145 will update the entire contents of the SILVA database. From release 144 onwards, we will no longer provide raw sequence data. All sequences, aligned and unaligned, will be truncated to the rRNA gene boundaries. We will introduce SILVA accession numbers

to reflect this change.

Additional data and quality improvements

We have started to manually re-evaluate all alignments in our alignment seed to improve the SILVA alignment for release 144. Additionally, we plan to continuously improve the coverage of the seed by adding manual alignments for species which are only distantly related to any of the contained sequences.

Many different tools (e.g. QIIME, DADA2) use SILVA as a reference dataset. These tools often require a fixed rank taxonomy, which SILVA does not provide. Therefore, the SILVA taxonomy is converted differently by each tool, making it difficult to compare results. To mitigate the issue, we will provide a Taxallnomy ([Sakamoto and Ortega, 2021](#)) version of the SILVA taxonomy beginning with release 144.

We plan to develop a concept and prototype to improve the classification of organelles in SILVA. They currently carry the taxonomic path of the organelle, but the species name of its putative host. Additionally, it is, so far, not (easily) possible to retrieve the classification of organelles based on their hosts – which is often more interesting than the fact that an organelle was found in a sample.

SILVA currently lacks a dedicated type strain and genome subset, ideally containing only one sequence per species. We plan to add this with release 145, using the in-house data and expertise of the DSMZ. Extending the concept to environmental sequences is a long term goal.

We will support the Data Integration team

in the development of the #MISO finder. At a later stage, the isolation source data generated by the tool will be added to SILVA. This data will not be available on the SILVA website until the website has been rebuilt (see technical improvements).

Technical improvements

Over the years, SILVA has grown into a large legacy code base. The current state makes maintenance and development difficult. We plan to consolidate and rewrite large parts of our software based on the lessons learned from running SILVA for over 15 years. We will rely heavily on containerisation to facilitate deployment, migration, and failover.

We have started to migrate the SILVA website jobs to Nextflow pipelines. We will then also port our release pipeline. The SILVA website is planned to be updated, both in

terms of design and technology. We are considering migrating to a different database technology to overcome the current limitations in terms of speed and sequence export size, which is required for the provision of an API. None of the existing website code can be reused. The task is dependent on filling the remaining developer position.

Quast, C., Priesse, E., Yilmaz, P., Gerken, J., Schweer, T., Yarza, P., Peplies, J., & Glöckner, F. O. (2013). The SILVA ribosomal RNA gene database project: improved data processing and web-based tools. *Nucleic acids research*, 41(Database issue), D590–D596. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gks1219>

Yilmaz, P., Parfrey, L. W., Yarza, P., Gerken, J., Priesse, E., Quast, C., Schweer, T., Peplies, J., Ludwig, W., & Glöckner, F. O. (2014). The SILVA and “All-species Living Tree Project (LTP)” taxonomic frameworks. *Nucleic acids research*, 42(Database issue), D643–D648. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkt1209>

Other Scientific Databases of the DSMZ

TYGS – Type (Strain) Genome Server

The Type (Strain) Genome Server [TYGS](#) is a state-of-the-art platform for prokaryotic genome-based taxonomy. The highly popular TYGS is a user-friendly, high-throughput web server providing genome-based species and subspecies delineation, automatic determination of closest relatives, phylogenomic analysis, interactive visualisation of trees, and comprehensive access to taxonomic and nomenclatural information. TYGS is strongly linked to LPSN and other DSMZ databases. The TYGS platform allows researchers worldwide to address questions in a wide variety of fields, including taxonomy, phylogenomics, biotechnology, medicine, biodiversity and metagenomics, in an easy and effortless way, thus advancing science by opening access to different types of data and analyses to a broad international community.

TYGS is the successor to the [GGDC](#) - a highly successful method for prokaryotic taxonomy with over 5,000 citations to date - and contains genomic, taxonomic and nomenclatural data on over 20,000 type strains (the backbone of prokaryotic systematics) and *Candidatus* species. The database is updated on a weekly basis. TYGS imports genome sequences from GenBank using the GenBank flat file format and from [IMG](#). All underlying nomenclature data are obtained from LPSN.

TYGS is [queried](#) via sequence data - essentially acting as a complex search string

- and users receive a tailored set of results once the query has been processed. This approach differs from most database approaches in that the complexity of genome-scale data affects the computational requirements of downstream operations, which take more time than a simple search string query in a database. Access to TYGS is free and the data reported are open access without restriction.

[TYGS results](#) are designed to be user-friendly and highly interoperable. Phylogenetic trees can be downloaded in Newick format. Their visual representation on TYGS is highly customizable and can be downloaded in PNG and SVG formats. References can be downloaded in BibTeX format. All data tables can be downloaded in PDF, CSV or XLS format. Particularly large datasets of pairwise digital DNA:DNA hybridisation (dDDH) results can also be downloaded in JSON format. All genome sequences are represented by identifiers in [INSDC](#), IMG and GOLD where possible. The original data are available from these sources in standard formats. Taxon names and strain identifiers are linked to LPSN, where the underlying information is available in standard formats, to culture collections, and to *BacDive*.

As of September 2023, TYGS had been accessed by researchers from 147 countries around the world. More than 10,000 different researchers had made more than

90,000 TYGS queries. As our [citation analysis](#) shows, c. 50% of the monthly users have used TYGS at least once before, indicating that many of them have integrated TYGS into their research routine. This is underlined by the over 2,000 citations of the two peer-reviewed TYGS publications.

TYGS should be further expanded, including the planned technical optimisations such as more time- and memory-efficient implementations. The aim was also to expand the analysis options, particularly with respect to linking to DSMZ's other databases. This work had to be postponed until the position of a bioinformatician for

phylogenomics could be filled. The older GDDC system is also heavily used but is now better integrated into TYGS in terms of both genomic calculations and the display of results.

Meier-Kolthoff, J. P., Carbasse, J. S., Peinado-Olarte, R. L., & Göker, M. (2022). TYGS and LPSN: a database tandem for fast and reliable genome-based classification and nomenclature of prokaryotes. *Nucleic acids research*, 50(D1), D801–D807. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab902>

Meier-Kolthoff, J. P., & Göker, M. (2019). TYGS is an automated high-throughput platform for state-of-the-art genome-based taxonomy. *Nature communications*, 10(1), 2182. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-10210-3>

MediaDive - The Cultivation Media Database

[MediaDive](#) is the world's largest database of cultivation media and growth conditions. It was developed in 2021 as part of the [Di-ASPora project](#). The aim of the project was to increase the availability of microbial data and to make it machine-readable to facilitate the application of artificial intelligence. More than 3,200 media recipes were mobilised and standardised. This dataset has been further enriched by adding growth conditions for more than 45,000 organisms from all domains of life.

MediaDive provides the standardised recipes with calculated final concentrations. The media recipes come from culture collections and individual scientists. The DSMZ has a full-featured editor interface to manually curate the recipes and add new media directly to the database. Recipes from other collections have been semi-automatically extracted and reviewed by their curators. Individuals can design their own media using the [Media Builder tool](#) and share them with the community.

Figure 10: Data that are comprised in the MediaDive database.

In addition to the cultivation media, *MediaDive* provides a number of tools for working with them. Users can find media by name, media number, [ingredients and their concentrations](#), and organisms growing on them. Media are also aggregated by the taxonomy of the organisms, allowing users to [find other media for related taxonomic groups](#). It is even possible to identify media used for organisms from specific [isolation sources](#). This is possible thanks to the integration of the *BacDive* isolation source ontology (currently only for prokaryotes); for example, one can search for prokaryotes isolated from beverage production and find that they often grow on MRS media.

Once a user has found a culture medium of interest, there are many ways to work with it. It is possible to adjust the final volume of the medium and make strain-specific adjustments, if any. These modifications are visible in the web interface, but are also applied when the medium is downloaded as a PDF. See for example [medium 1011c for strain DSM 22050](#). In addition, users can generate a QR code in the desktop browser to more easily switch to the mobile version. The mobile interface offers a dedicated cooking guide for the media, focusing on the recipe and allowing users to tick off the ingredients they have already added to the media. In addition, *MediaDive* provides an [open API](#) to automatically retrieve information about media recipes, final compositions, ingredients and strains to programmatically work with growing media.

MediaDive is one of the newer members of the DSMZ Digital Diversity, but has gained popularity and influence. Over the past year, *MediaDive* has had about 5,000 unique visitors per month. In total, we had

about 58,000 visitors in 2023, with 35,000 unique IP addresses.

In the next years we plan to connect *MediaDive* with the other databases of DSMZ Digital Diversity. Currently, *MediaDive* is well connected to the *BacDive* database, but it will also benefit from links and integrations with LPSN, StrainInfo and *PhageDive*. We will also be working on the integration of cell line culture media, which will contribute to the integration with *DSMZCellDive*. We also plan to extend the Isolation Source Finder prototype with more search options and add fungal isolation sources, which will happen in close collaboration with *BacDive* and SILVA. Finally, we will integrate our first prototype of an AI-based media prediction tool. This tool uses the standardised cultivation media, genome annotations and machine learning algorithms, i.e. Random Forest and *k*-Nearest Neighbour, to suggest the best cultivation conditions for an uploaded (meta-)genome sequence. A first prototype is currently being tested in the DSMZ laboratories and will be released to *MediaDive* later this year. Until the end of 2023 *MediaDive* has been developed by Julia Koblitz, who has taken over the development of the Digital Diversity Hub. As of now no dedicated funding is allocated for the development of *MediaDive*, which is why the time frame of further developments is unclear.

Koblitz, J., Halama, P., Spring, S., Thiel, V., Baschien, C., Hahnke, R. L., Pester, M., Overmann, J., & Reimer, L. C. (2023). *MediaDive*: the expert-curated cultivation media database. *Nucleic acids research*, 51(D1), D1531–D1538. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac803>

DSMZCellDive - Tools and Data on Cell Lines

[DSMZCellDive](#) is a database and web tool developed in 2022 to help researchers select the best model cell line for their research. To accomplish this task, it provides a variety of data on nearly 1,000 cell lines from the DSMZ, including [RNA-seq expression data](#), [Short Tandem Repeats \(STR\) profiles](#), [cytochrome c oxidase I \(COI\) DNA barcodes](#), [Human leukocyte antigen \(HLA\) typing](#), and morphology and cultivation information. The data are currently curated and maintained by the Human and Animal Cell Lines Department of the DSMZ. In particular, the RNA-seq dataset, which is currently only available for 139 human cancer cell lines, is constantly being expanded.

DSMZCellDive provides expression data that can be visualised as bar charts or heat maps. Individual genes or sets of more than 20,000 human genes can be selected for analysis in the plots. In addition, different tumour entities or cell lines can be selected. DSMZCellDive also includes a full-featured STR profile search with 17 supported STR loci and more than 4,630 profiles.

The core of DSMZCellDive are the individual pages for [cell lines](#) or [genes](#), which integrate the different data types described above. A cell line page, e.g. for the [HL-60](#) cell line, provides general information, including the Accession number (ACC) and a link to the DSMZ catalogue, information on cell type and species origin, accompanied by cultivation information, morphology and tumour type. Another tab displays RNA-seq data, if available. It includes two histograms and a link to the full RNA-seq analysis tool. If the cell line is human, an STR profile is also displayed, while for animal cell lines,

COI DNA barcoding reports are provided. If available, HLA typing information and morphology images are also included.

DSMZCellDive has had an increasing number of visitors since its release in 2022. More than 16,000 visitors were recorded in 2023, belonging to about 8,600 unique IP addresses.

For future development, DSMZCellDive will strengthen the connection with other databases, including external databases such as [Cellosaurus](#), as well as other databases from the DSMZ Digital Diversity such as BRENDA or MediaDive. In cooperation with Amos Bairoch of Cellosaurus, the two databases will be linked and integrated, which will further increase the visibility of DSMZCellDive. Further plans include the integration of other data types, such as mutation data and SNP array data, and the development of an open API for automated data retrieval. In cooperation with BRENDA, new signal transduction pathways will be mapped and an interface will be developed within the next two years. This will allow the visualisation of expression data on comprehensive pathway maps. Until now DSMZCellDive has been developed by Julia Koblitz, who has taken over the development of the Digital Diversity Hub. As of now no dedicated funding is allocated for the development of DSMZCellDive, which is why the time frame of further developments is unclear.

Koblitz, J., Dirks, W. G., Eberth, S., Nagel, S., Steenpass, L., & Pommerenke, C. (2022). DSMZCellDive: Diving into high-throughput cell line data. *F1000Research*, 11, 420. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.111175.2>

PhageDive - Trait Data on Phages

PhageDive is a database providing detailed information on 1,167 bacteriophages and archaeal viruses. It was first developed within the [SPP 2330 project](#) in 2022, by Joaquim Sardá, Lorenz Reimer, Johannes Wittmann and Clara Rolland. After a first prototype in September 2022, the first full release of the database was published in summer 2023. PhageDive is based on the BacDive technology and gathers all existing data on prokaryotic viruses that are dispersed across multiple sources, like scientific publications, specialised databases or internal files of culture collections. PhageDive provides fields for various experimental data (lifestyle, lysis kinetics, adsorption kinetics, host range, genomic data, etc.) and all available metadata (e.g., geographical origin, isolation source). One highlight are detailed electron microscopy images of 494 strains ([example](#)). An important feature is to link experimental data to the culture collection number and the repository of the corresponding physical bioresource (virus and prokaryotic host strains). To date, PhageDive covers 1,167 phages from three different world-renowned collections

(DSMZ, [Canada's Laval collection](#) and the [UK's NCTC](#)). Similar to BacDive, PhageDive interlinks information with other databases such as [NCBI](#), the Institut Pasteur's Viral host range database ([VHRdb](#)) or BacDive and MediaDive. The [advanced search](#) function allows querying up to 70 data fields and thereby enables researchers to find viral strains based on their attributes like host species, propagation or genomic data. The latest development is a genome browser that allows users to quickly get an overview of the genome and explore the genes of a phage ([example](#)). The future development of PhageDive is dependent on the contribution of further collections and on the feedback from the user community. As of now no dedicated funding is allocated for the development of PhageDive, which is why the time frame of further developments is unclear.

Rolland, C., Wittmann, J., Reimer, L.C., Sardà Carbasse, J., Schober, I., Dudek, C.-A., Ebeling, C., Koblitz, J., Bunk, B. and Overmann, J. (2024) PhageDive: the comprehensive strain database of prokaryotic viral diversity. *Nucleic Acids Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae878>

StrainInfo - Microbial Strain Identifiers

The StrainInfo database collects microbial identifiers, depicts their relations and links them to taxonomy, sequences, and literature. It aims to be a comprehensive resource for strain identity information that supports microbiologists in easily and quickly collecting information on a strain that may be known under a myriad of different designations and IDs in publications

and databases. This will help to overcome significant hurdles in the communication of research findings and the comparison and reuse of data.

The foundation for the StrainInfo database was laid in 2000, when a team at the Belgian bacterial culture collection [BCCM/LMG](#), located at the University of Ghent, started to collect strain IDs from different

culture collections and other sources for the resolution of microbial strain designations. In 2007, the resulting database was made public as StrainInfo.net and evolved into a well-established and highly used resource in the following years. Despite the popularity of the webservice, the development of StrainInfo.net had to be discontinued in 2015 due to lack of funding. As a consequence, the website went offline in 2019.

The complete data was later transferred to the DSMZ and, starting in 2021, a new version of the StrainInfo database and website was developed as a service and use case of the [NFDI4Microbiota](#) consortium, by Artur Lissin, Isabel Schober and Lorenz Reimer. Officially released in September 2023, the new StrainInfo has a completely redesigned database structure, backend and user interface. The archive data were expanded by new data from the catalogues of the culture collection at the University of Gothenburg ([CCUG](#)), the collection of the Institut Pasteur ([CIP](#)) and the DSMZ and the database now contains 289,910 strains, consisting of 449,715 cultures or instances of strains with identifiers or designations that are cultured in one laboratory or collection.

Apart from strain identifiers, StrainInfo collects and displays culture-specific information associated with them in the respective culture collection catalogues, including the listed taxonomy, depositor, deposition year and the designation provided at deposition (Example strain page: <https://straininfo.dsmz.de/strain/14146>). This information allows us to draw conclusions about the exchange history of the strain. While StrainInfo currently only displays a shallow

history with the immediate ancestor and immediate descendants of a culture, in the future we envision a representation of complete strain histories as rooted trees. Every strain in the database is referenced by a DOI. To ensure the citability, a new DOI version is generated whenever strain data are changed and old versions are available for download in a special archive section.

We are currently working on validating, cleaning and bringing up to date the sequences and publications linked in StrainInfo, which in the current release still almost completely consists of archive data that had not been updated since 2015.

In the future, StrainInfo plans to offer a strain registration and deposition management service called StrainRegistry. It will allow microbiologists to register strains with strain meta- and deposition data, which are not published, but can directly be shared with a participating culture collection. The StrainRegistry user interface will visualise the deposition status of each strain and facilitate communication between the depositor and the responsible culture collection curator, who can view strain information, demand further data, request shipping of biological material and change strain status. When strains have been checked by a curator, they will receive a persistent DOI and be published in the StrainInfo database. This procedure is being developed in collaboration with the curators of the DSMZ to simplify bulk deposition at the DSMZ and with the ambition to engage other culture collections and standardise microbial strain deposition worldwide. The development of StrainInfo is funded by NFDI4Microbiota until September 2026.

The DSMZ Digital Diversity

As seen from the report so far, the DSMZ hosts several individual databases covering a wide range of biological areas. Although there are already some links between the databases, the aim of the DSMZ Digital Diversity is to take the connection to the next level and create something bigger. In the following sections, we will look beyond the development of individual databases and

focus on projects that the DSMZ Digital Diversity team will develop together.

To do this, we have set up a new working group called Data Integration, which is dedicated to integrating all the databases and developing new applications and techniques. This group is led by Julia Koblitz.

1: The Digital Diversity Hub

The Digital Diversity Hub (hub.dsmz.de) is a website that pursues two goals. Firstly, it is the central portal for the newly built bio-data infrastructure, informing users about the infrastructure itself, the databases and current developments. Secondly, it will be the main resource for implementing the ideas outlined below. The Hub will be the stage for all new tools and developments that go beyond a single database.

Federated search

One particular development is an all-encompassing search across all databases. It will be possible to search for any term associated with an entity in any database and find it through the Hub. Even though this task seems pretty forward, it harbours some challenges that we are currently facing. The most important challenge is the readiness of all the databases. Each of them has different requirements: some provide data already via an API, others can only be fetched via manual ex- and imports; some of the databases rely on web technologies that do not yet provide (persistent) links to

their entities, which is why linking to them is not yet possible. In conclusion, the databases must first reach a level of readiness to be integrated into the Digital Diversity Hub, including but not limited to the new microbial exchange format of *BacDive*, the new SILVA accession numbers and type strain datasets, the BRENDA gene and taxonomy improvements, and improvement of the LPSN API.

However, we decided to start with a smaller number of entities and search terms and developed a first prototype of the federated search. While this will be released in mid of 2024, we will continue to improve the search with more sophisticated search algorithms. We will further include more entities and data points and also plan to integrate the [DSMZ catalogue](#).

Integrated Data Profile for Bioresources

The Leibniz Institute DSMZ is home to 65,000 bioresources that are sold to 87 different countries around the world. These bioresources include bacteria, archaea, fungi including yeasts, human and animal cell lines, protists, bacteriophages and plant viruses. A large number of datasets are

collection numbers, sequences, literature, cultivation, taxonomy & nomenclature, gene expression, morphology, physiology and origin of individual microbes and cell lines.

Therefore, we plan to integrate all available data for all DSMZ bioresources into a digital supplement that will be added to customer orders, but also published on the Hub according to [FAIR principles](#). This will serve as a comprehensive source for all information

Figure 11: Overview on all databases that will be integrated into the Digital Diversity Hub.

generated for all these resources, many of which are made publicly available through our databases. These data are further supplemented by literature collected through text mining and manual annotation, e.g. in the BacDive and BRENDA databases, and by mining external databases. All in all, we have information on identifiers and culture

on a microbe or cell line from the DSMZ, with links to further information and tools in the databases.

The team plans to have a first prototype available in the Digital Diversity Hub by the end of this year. Due to problems with

recruitment, particularly for the SILVA database, this prototype may not include all databases at launch, but will be expanded as soon as possible. Furthermore, we are going to collect and incorporate user feedback from scientists at DSMZ, from the regional research infrastructure, and at (international) conferences. We plan to integrate user feedback and remaining features to have the first production release online until mid of 2025. Initially we will focus on our own resources and data, but in the future we may extend the integration to bioresources from other collections

and other external databases (e.g. [INSDC](#), [Cellosaurus](#), etc.).

Publication

It is planned to publish the Digital Diversity Hub including an overview on all featured databases, the federated search and the integrated data profile for bioresources mid of 2025 in the *Nucleic Acid Research* (NAR) database issue. We plan to emphasise the collaboration between databases, the novel possibilities and will give a look ahead.

2: A novel Plant Virus Database

It is noticeable that our databases cover almost all of the DSMZ bioresources that can be integrated into the Digital Diversity Hub. Some of the databases cover a wider range of organisms, e.g. SILVA, BRENDA and *MediaDive*, others focus on a particular domain or group of organisms, e.g. *BacDive*, covering prokaryotes, *PhageDive*, covering bacteriophages and *CellDive*, which focuses on cell lines. However, two of the DSMZ bioresources are not currently covered by a dedicated database, namely fungi and plant viruses. For fungi, the number of well-established databases is immense, e.g. [Mycobank](#), [Index Fungorum](#) and [FungiDB](#). However, this is not the case for plant viruses. The number of available online resources focusing on plant viruses is small and existing databases are often non-standardised collections of articles (e.g. [DPVweb](#)) or are no longer maintained (e.g. Plant Viruses Online, [Indian Plant Virus DB](#)).

Recognising the need for a dedicated plant

virus database and in order to integrate data on plant viruses into the Digital Diversity Hub (see section 1), we plan to share the data we already have in-house in a novel dedicated plant virus database. In fact, the DSMZ has a large amount of data that is not yet published, e.g. via our online catalogue. This includes host-pathogen interactions, thousands of host RNA-seq datasets, REM images, genome sequences and numerous images of plant hosts at different stages of infection (Figure 12). All these data will be mined and used to build a new database of plant viruses. The database with all its features and specific tools (e.g. RNA-seq visualisation, genome browser, host interaction network) will be a stand-alone platform, although derived data will also contribute to the integrated bioresource data profiles.

We envision a three year development phase of the plant virus database (once the position is filled), including the mobilisation of existing datasets and partial releases in

the form of alpha and beta states of the database. This phase will be followed by a

collaboration with experts from the plant virus department at the DSMZ and a net-

Figure 12: The data contents of the proposed Plant Virus Database.

first publication and a detailed evaluation before further decisions are made on the continuation of the project. The development of the database will be done in close

work of experts worldwide. We plan to collect feedback and user stories at different stages of the project.

3: The Digital Diversity Knowledge Graph

As highlighted earlier, there are a huge number of datasets available from our databases. However, it is not just the number of data points that is large, but also the diversity of the data. Although our focus is on data on bioresources of the DSMZ, this includes data on phenotypes, cultivation, metabolism, sequences, identity, taxonomy and much more. In Figure 13, we have developed a first draft of the top-level ontology, which nicely shows the complexity

of this network and how all data are connected in some way.

We already made first advancements in the field of knowledge graphs within the [DiASPora project](#) that ended this spring. In this project, a first knowledge graph was developed for the BacDive database. The BacDive SPARQL endpoint that serves as an entry point to the knowledge graph will be integrated mid of this year and will serve as a pilot model for further ideas and

The ontology, graph and knowledge discovery tool will be developed over the next

three years, depending on the successful filling of the open position.

4: Organism-specific Metabolic Pathway Maps

In this project, we will make partial use of the BRENDA database, which contains a huge collection of enzymatic reactions and pathways that have been manually curated. However, the BRENDA pathway map is currently overly complex with 188 pathways from many organisms, more than 2,700 enzyme nodes and more than 6,500 metabolite and cofactor nodes. Even within a single pathway, there are often multiple routes or alternative enzymes, some of which are specific to a particular taxonomic range (Figure 14). BRENDA has

a search function to highlight pathways that are found in a particular organism, but this does not reduce the complexity of the map (Figure 14B). As the maps are currently drawn by hand, it is neither easy nor time efficient to add new pathways or reduce the complexity of the map.

We will develop a toolbox to automatically draw pathways based on the biochemical reactions in BRENDA, automatic genome annotations and further data provided by the other databases such as BacDive and MediaDive. The new toolbox will help us

Figure 14: Schema of the serine metabolism pathway maps in BRENDA. A) Current status of the map at maximum zoom level without adjustments. B) Current status of the map when selecting the genus *Saccharolobus* as reference taxon. Highlighted in yellow are all enzymes where data are present in BRENDA (manually annotated) or in SwissProt. C) Our vision of an improved pathway presentation. What is not present and not needed will be left out and a more straight-forward representation makes the pathway easier to capture and understand. Furthermore, gaps are indicated clearly (2.7.1.31) as well as different levels of annotation that are indicated by colour (e.g. manually curated vs. automatically annotated). Experimental evidence of metabolites can be drawn from other databases (e.g. BacDive) and indicated as well (the red asterisk).

expand our pathway portfolio more easily: it will be possible to add new pathway maps more quickly and to have individual pathway pages in addition to the overarching pathway map. It will also be possible to reduce the pathway map to an organism-specific set of pathways and to simplify the pathways to those that are actually used by the organism. These organism specific pathways will be better visualised and will also feature more details on the level of annotation (Figure 14C). We will initially focus on prokaryotes, with the prospect of extending this to other organisms in the future. The main challenge will be to develop algorithms that can visualise pathways from the underlying reaction data while respecting conventions, such as the presentation and direction of cycles and alternative routes. It will also be challenging to deal with annotation gaps in the organism-specific pathways and to design the user experience in this regard.

However, to start this project, reaction

data first have to be transformed into a graph format in order to enable graph-based queries, identify gaps and facilitate already implemented graph visualisations. Afterwards, the graph data can be used to develop novel algorithms and strategies for the display of pathway maps with regard to previously mentioned conventions. This will result in a toolbox to visualise pathway maps from graph data that we plan to publish accordingly. Next, we will look into genome annotations, evaluate and improve various algorithms and start with a subset of model species to develop the first organism-specific pathways. While we continue to improve the process, we plan to involve users early by integrating first pathway prototypes into BRENDA and BacDive. In total, this project is planned for the next three years, with Anja Tietz starting in mid-May as the main developer.

5: Acceleration of Data Curation through Text Mining-powered Annotation Suite

As mentioned in the description of our databases, some of them rely heavily on annotation of literature. The BRENDA enzyme database has over 167,000 manually curated references, while the BacDive database has around 57,000 and LPSN has over 28,000 references. Most of these data, especially in BRENDA and BacDive, are manually annotated by student research assistants and external curation experts, making the process lengthy and error-prone.

Using machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) techniques, we will transform the manual annotation process in the future. In a pilot project (DiAS-Pora), we gained relevant experience with NLP and started to develop an integrated set of annotation modules for the BacDive database. However, the functionality is still very basic and needs further development in terms of data standardisation and its user interface. In addition, the text mining models and interface need to be extended

to meet the needs of the other databases.

Currently, we are planning a modular approach (Figure 15), which would allow the tool to be extended with other databases, e.g. the planned plant virus database. Users will have two roles: they can either be an *editor* who oversees the annotation process, or an *annotator* who does the actual annotation. The editor will select literature to annotate, which will be automatically captured by the annotation tool. A pre-trained text mining model will then extract the information from the text. The actual curation tool will combine the text corpus with the text-mined annotations and present the extracted data to the annotator in the context of the publication. The annotator can now confirm, reject or modify the annotations, which are fed back to retrain the model. The final annotation is reviewed by the editor and can then be automatically transformed into the database. The system will automatically perform plausibility checks and return warnings to the editor. Ideally, all communication will take place using the annotation suite itself, from the selection of the publication to the integration of extracted data into the database, which alone will save a considerable amount of time. The system can be extended with various other features, such as automatic synonym checks for chemical compound names.

The development of such an annotation suite as an integrated set of modules is another long-term project and will take

three years once the position is filled. However, we expect our annotations to become much more time efficient with the aim of annotating new publications as soon as they are published.

Figure 15: Proposed schema of the annotation suite. A modular approach enables easy configuration and development of custom modules.

6: Microbial Isolation Sources

The information where a strain was found is usually provided in databases

as an *isolation source* and is associated with most isolated microbial strains. For

microbiologists the source of isolation is of high interest as it can be used to infer cultivation conditions or even a possible ecological role of a species. However, this information is provided in various formats ranging from a single word like “soil” to a very detailed description that contains every detail recorded during the sampling. This makes even simple queries like “all microorganisms found in the marine environment” for a large dataset almost impossible. To overcome this problem the BacDive team together with the DSMZ department of Bioresources for Bioeconomy and Health Research has developed a small ontology to supplement original isolation source entries with a set of tags, similar to hash tags used in social media. Compared to other ontologies, the **Microbial Isolation Source Ontology (#MISO)** is restricted to a small and clear vocabulary of 380 terms organised in a maximum of three levels of hierarchy and with only 8 first-level terms. #MISO shares only 141 classes with other ontologies that are either specialised to environmental data (Environmental Ontology,

ENVO) or to medical data (Medical Subject Headings, MESH and National Cancer Institute Thesaurus, NCIT).

As mentioned, the #MISO has been developed to allow systematic analysis of and search within isolation sources. This is why an [isolation source search tool](#) exists in BacDive comprising data on 54,578 prokaryotic strains and we furthermore assigned #MISO tags to more than 46,937 strains from the fungal collections of DSMZ and the [Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute](#).

Even with the already sophisticated isolation search from BacDive, the high potential of isolation sources represents a significant opportunity that has remained largely unexplored. Connecting isolation sources with cultivation media could lead to innovative cultivation approaches, offering new insights and applications in the field of microbiology. Similarly, linking isolation sources with microbial traits may result in novel deductions, deepening our understanding of the microbial world.

Figure 16: Overview on the Microbial Isolation Source Ontology (#MISO). A) The first level of #MISO consists of 8 different terms. B) Isolation sources are mostly textual descriptions of the source the organism was obtained from. In the future, the #MISO Finder will be developed and applied to transform the unstructured text into the standardised ontology.

However, it is important to note that annotating isolation sources requires trained personnel and a substantial time investment, potentially limiting scalability and efficiency. This is why we are going to develop an AI-guided approach that can leverage the large manually curated datasets of more than 100,000 isolation sources to automate this process. By doing so, it will accelerate the process and enable the incorporation of millions of isolation sources from the SILVA database.

In detail, this project can be divided into the following work packages:

Improvement of the #MISO ontology: The initial phase of the project will focus on refining and expanding the Microbial Isolation Source Ontology (#MISO). This will involve a reverse engineering process to ensure that #MISO effectively captures the diverse range of isolation sources encountered in microbial research.

Development of the AI-based prediction approach: Concurrently, efforts will be directed towards developing an AI-guided prediction approach for annotating isolation sources with #MISO tags. This will involve training machine learning algorithms on the existing manually curated dataset to recognize patterns and associations

between isolation sources, cultivation media, and microbial traits.

Integration of #MISO-Finder tool into the Digital Diversity Hub: Upon completion of the AI-based prediction approach, the resulting #MISO-Finder tool will be integrated into the Digital Diversity Hub platform under the FAIR principles. This integration will provide researchers with a user-friendly interface to access and utilise the annotated isolation sources, thereby facilitating more efficient data analysis and search functionalities. It will be furthermore the point in the timeline where we can publish the ontology alongside the tools.

Integration of new data in our databases: As the project progresses, efforts will be made to integrate the newly annotated isolation sources into the *BacDive*, SILVA and *MediaDive* databases. This will involve updating the databases with the latest information and ensuring seamless interoperability between #MISO-Finder and these existing resources. Additionally, ongoing efforts will be made to incorporate new data into these databases to continuously enrich the available microbial diversity information.